

WANDERING EARTH AND ITS WANDERING WORDS: A PILOT STUDY OF INDIRECT SUBTITLING OF CHINESE CINEMA INTO SPANISH VIA ENGLISH

Yuchen Liu, cielolyc@gmail.com

Minghao Ma, maminghao@shisu.edu.cn

Shanghai International Studies University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19328210>

Keywords: indirect translation, Chinese cinema, corpus study, subtitling, Chinese-Spanish translation

As film circulation accelerates under globalisation and increasingly contributes to a country's soft power projection, audiovisual translation (AVT) plays a crucial role in mediating cultural exchange. Despite the growing international presence of Chinese cinema, its "going global" trajectory continues to face constraints linked to debatable translation quality, uneven audience reception, and limited dissemination channels (Xiao & Chen, 2024). Against the backdrop of deepening China-Hispanic cultural ties, shaped by initiatives such as the Belt and Road and the 50th anniversary of China-Spain diplomatic relations, research on the translation of Chinese cinema into Spanish remains comparatively scarce. Previous mapping work suggests that, in Spain, many Chinese films are distributed through mediating languages, most notably English, often due to cost and workflow efficiency considerations (Casas-Tost & Rovira-Esteva, 2019). At the same time, indirect translation has garnered growing interest among AVT scholars in recent years, with quality-related concerns repeatedly being foregrounded (Baños, Dalli, & Díaz-Cintas, 2025; Pięta, 2024).

This pilot study aims to examine potential indirect subtitling practices in the context of the Chinese blockbuster sci-fi film *The Wandering Earth I* (2019) on Netflix. It analyses the platform's two Spanish subtitle variants (Castilian Spanish and Latin American Spanish) against the Chinese dialogue and the English subtitle track, treating English as a mediating language. Using a comparative multimodal approach, the analysis focuses on converging indicators of pivot-mediated transfer. In addition, it considers this film's reception among Hispanic audiences to contextualise its circulation and uptake. The findings seek to shed light on the complexities and implications of indirect translation in contemporary Chinese film distribution.

References:

1. Baños, R., Dalli, H., & Díaz-Cintas, J. (2025). Pivot subtitling workflows in the age of streaming platforms. *Translation & Interpreting: The International Journal of Translation and Interpreting Research*, 17(2), 16-37.
2. Casas-Tost, H., & Rovira-Esteva, S. (2019). Chinese cinema in Spain: an overview through audiovisual translation. *Babel*, 65(4): 582-604.
3. Pięta, H., Valdez, S., Menezes, R., & Sokoli, S. (2024). Indirect (pivot) audiovisual translation: a burning issue for research and training. *Perspectives*, 32(5), 763-779.
4. Xiao, J., and Chen, X. (2024). Zhongguo dianying haiwai chuanbo xianzhuang, wenti ji yingdui [Current situation, problems, and countermeasures of Chinese films' overseas communication]. *Dianying Wenxue (Film Literature)*, 13, 145-148.